

What Changed? Detecting and Evaluating Instruction-Guided Image Edits with Multimodal Large Language Models

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Figure 1. Qualitative examples from DICE. Our approach detects differences between an original image and an edited one, identifying the involved objects and the type of edit. Further, DICE evaluates each difference to determine its coherence with the editing prompt.

Abstract

Instruction-based image editing models offer increased personalization opportunities in generative tasks. However, properly evaluating their results is challenging, and most of the existing metrics lag in terms of alignment with human judgment and explainability. To tackle these issues, we introduce **DICE** (**D**ifference **C**oherence **E**stimator), a model designed to detect localized differences between the original and the edited image and to assess their relevance to the given modification request. DICE consists of two key components: a difference detector and a coherence estimator, both built on an autoregressive Multimodal Large Language Model (MLLM) and trained using a strategy that leverages self-supervision, distillation from inpainting networks, and full supervision. Through extensive experiments, we evaluate each stage of our pipeline, comparing different MLLMs within the proposed framework. We demonstrate that DICE effectively identifies coherent edits, effectively evaluating images generated by different editing models with a strong correlation with human judgment. We publicly release our source code, models, and data at [project page](#).

1. Introduction

The field of Generative AI has recently gained significant attention in both industry and research, driven by the development of models capable of generating content that closely follows the distribution of natural language [1, 14, 21] and real images [15, 39, 43]. Thanks to the availability of cross-modal operators and architectures, multimodal generative approaches, which can seamlessly integrate both the vision and language modalities, are reaching increasing levels of accuracy [6, 32, 49, 52]. These advancements are driving the development of new applications and tasks while enhancing user control over the generation process.

Among these proposals, instruction-based image editing models [4, 18, 25, 54] enable the modification of an input image based on a free-form textual instruction from the user. This extends traditional text-to-image models, shifting the focus from generating an image from scratch to modifying an existing one while adhering to a given prompt. While

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such models promise to offer increased personalization levels, the understanding of the results they generate (and thus their proper evaluation) clearly becomes more challenging than in traditional text-to-image contexts.

Prior work has approached the evaluation of image editing models by developing annotated benchmarks with ground-truth edited images [45, 46, 54] or by proposing metrics based on pre-trained backbones such as CLIP [40] and DINO [8]. Other methods leverage pre-trained large language models to assess the quality of image edits [3, 27, 35]. While these proposals might offer a first viable solution to assess the performance of image editing models, they still do not reach a sufficient alignment with human evaluation. Further, being based on either global embedding vectors or replies from pre-trained (and often private) models, explaining their evaluations becomes cumbersome.

Drawing inspiration from these considerations, we take a novel approach and propose a learnable model for understanding localized image edits, which can provide increased alignment with human preferences and more easily explainable results. Although instruction-guided image editing encompasses a broad range of possible transformations, this work focuses on object-level edits, motivated by the observation that precise, localized modifications remain a significant challenge for generative models and thus require specialized evaluation protocols. Accordingly, our model first identifies object-level differences between the original and the edited images and subsequently evaluates the coherence of each detected modification relative to the user’s input instruction. We term our pipeline as **DICE**, short for **D**ifference **C**oherence **E**stimator. Sample results from our model are shown in Fig. 1.

Maintaining the goal of creating a fully explainable pipeline, we develop two distinct models, one for each stage, both built on an autoregressive Multimodal Large Language Model (MLLM) [6]. While both models leverage the understanding of RoIs, the first primarily focuses on their prediction, whereas the second emphasizes their interpretation to assess coherence with the given prompt. In particular, we first propose a difference detector that, given both images, estimates a set of localized differences that describe the change in content from one image to the other. The model also predicts the category of detected modifications, as either addition, removal, or editing of an object. A second model, based on the same architecture, is instead trained to predict the coherence of an object-level modification with respect to the modification request made by the user and provide a textual rationale for each decision made.

We experimentally assess the appropriateness of our strategy by carefully investigating the performance of both our difference detector and our coherence estimator, in comparison with existing solutions, and when employing different MLLMs. Further, we conduct a dedicated user study

to measure the alignment of the evaluations predicted by our proposal in terms of model ranking and evaluation. Experimental results demonstrate that our proposal achieves increased ranking capabilities while benefiting from an explainable-by-default approach. Further, when integrated into existing metrics, it acts as the basis for building model evaluation metrics with increased human alignment.

2. Related Work

Image Editing Models. Recent developments in Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [20, 28] and diffusion models [13, 15, 39, 43] have driven the rise of AI-generated content. However, users increasingly demand not only the creation of new visual data but also the modification of existing images, altering properties such as style [17, 28] and content [4, 16]. Within this domain, tasks vary based on the input used for conditioning. Image inpainting [10, 47], for instance, uses user-designed masks to guide edits in specific regions. In contrast, our work focuses on instruction-based image editing, where the model relies solely on textual instructions and the original image.

Within instruction-based editing, traditional approaches rely on diffusion models fine-tuned for instruction following. A fundamental contribution in this domain is InstructPix2Pix [4], which is trained on fully synthetic triplets composed of an input image, an editing instruction, and the edited image. However, since reliance on synthetic data may introduce noise, MagicBrush [54] refines the InstructPix2Pix framework using a high-quality, curated dataset. Differently, InstructDiffusion [18] is trained to perform a wide variety of tasks, including image editing and grounding. Further, HIVE [55] proposes a reward-based training that incorporates human feedback to enhance its instruction following capabilities. Differently, MGIE [16] employs a frozen MLLM to generate concise edit instructions that guide the diffusion model during image editing, whereas SmartEdit [26] captures the interactions between image and text via MLLM, improving prompt understanding.

Image Editing Evaluation and Benchmarks. Instruction-based image editing models have traditionally been evaluated along two dimensions: prompt adherence and background preservation. The former assesses the extent to which the output aligns with the given prompt instruction, whereas the latter evaluates the preservation of the unmodified contextual information. While benchmarks featuring annotated ground-truth edited images are available [45, 46, 54], our work prioritizes a reference-free evaluation that eliminates the need for human-defined labels. In this setting, background preservation is typically evaluated by using either CLIP [40] or DINO [8] to compute cosine similarities between the visual tokens extracted from the source and edited images [4, 16, 55]. Likewise, prompt adherence is usually quantified using CLIP-based similarities

Figure 2. Illustration of DICE. We employ an MLLM and fine-tune it for two different tasks. In the first stage (difference detection), the MLLM is trained to detect semantic differences between the original image and the edited one. In the second stage (coherence estimation), the MLLM is instructed to analyze and assess the coherence of each detected difference with respect to the given user prompt.

between the target caption and the edited image [44, 54].

With the recent proposal of MLLMs, these methods have been employed for prompt adherence evaluation. For instance, in HQ-Edit [27], GPT-4V [1] is used to assess coherence and alignment metrics. Additionally, I²E Bench [35] incorporates human annotation for certain queries, subsequently leveraging GPT-4V for question answering. However, reliance on GPT-based evaluations introduces potential variability and reproducibility issues, as model updates may alter the final scores. In contrast, we propose an interpretable solution based on an open-source MLLM, thereby increasing both the rationale behind our scoring mechanism and the reproducibility of the results.

Multimodal Large Language Models. With the introduction of LLM, the research community has put great effort into connecting visual modalities with textual reasoning [5, 11, 32]. Building on these efforts, MLLMs have also been used to address visual grounding tasks. Among these, Shikra [9] leverages a novel training paradigm to give the MLLM the capacity to reason with bounding boxes, making it able to precisely locate objects and relations in the image. Similarly, LISA [29] and GROUNDHOG [56] perform segmentation incorporating pixel-level representations for fine-grained visual understanding.

Compared to existing MLLMs for visual grounding, our model leverages multiple images to detect semantic differences, introducing a novel setting that requires an MLLM capable of multi-image understanding. In this context, Idefics3 [30] is able to comprehend multiple visual inputs interleaved with text, using a novel image encoding pipeline. Differently, Qwen [49] extends classical multimodal capabilities to video and multi-image understanding thanks to a novel encoding strategy and positional embedding technique for the visual inputs. Finally, mPLUG-Owl3 [52] introduces a novel attention-based strategy to ef-

ficiently encode long image sequences. Building on these multi-image models, we extend the capabilities of MLLMs by introducing a novel framework for multi-image detection, enabling the identification of semantic differences across multiple images within a unified system.

3. Proposed Method

3.1. Preliminaries

The objective of our approach is to assess the quality of outputs generated by instruction-based image editing models [4, 16, 55]. Formally, given an original image x and a textual instruction t , an image editing method f generates a new image $e = f(x, t)$, which incorporates the modifications specified by the textual prompt t , while preserving the contextual integrity of x .

While the modifications introduced by image editing models can be diverse – owing to the expressiveness of textual instructions and the flexibility of generative models – we focus specifically on object-level modifications. By means of this choice, we consider transformations that are clearly localizable inside the input scene. In particular, we assume that the original image contains a finite set of objects, denoted as $\{o_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and that the textual instruction t specifies an operation to be applied to it. Given a correct application of the specified operation, the expected edited image, denoted as \tilde{e} , serves as the ground-truth for evaluating the intended modification.

Object-level Modifications. Without loss of generality, we assume that the alterations required in the textual prompt can be classified as either the addition, removal, or modification of objects inside the input image. Specifically, we consider three categories of alterations, namely:

1. **Addition of an object.** A new object instance o_{n+1} is introduced into the scene, yielding a new image repre-

sensation. Treating images as a set of objects, and with a slight abuse of notation, this operation results in a new image that can be expressed as $\tilde{e} = (\bigcup_{i=1}^n o_i) \cup \{o_{n+1}\}$.

2. **Removal of an object.** The operation removes an object o_j which was present in the original image, which results in $\tilde{e} = (\bigcup_{i=1}^{j-1} o_i \cup \bigcup_{i=j+1}^n o_i)$.
3. **Edit of an object.** An existing object o_j is altered in at least one visual aspect. Let \tilde{o}_j denote the modified object; the updated image is then represented as $\tilde{e} = (\bigcup_{i=1}^n o_i \setminus \{o_j\}) \cup \{\tilde{o}_j\}$.

3.2. Overview of the Approach

An image editing network can produce an image e that does not accurately respect all the object-level operations required to produce \tilde{e} . To quantify this discrepancy, we propose **Difference Coherence Estimator (DICE)**: a two-step approach in which (i) we detect the object-level differences between the edited and the original image and then (ii) we evaluate the coherence of each difference with the textual prompt to determine whether a discrepancy reflects the intended modifications or constitutes an unwanted alteration. An overview of the two stages of DICE is depicted in Fig. 2.

Difference Detection. In this stage, we extract the set of objects that are present in the original image x but absent or changed in the predicted image e or vice versa. We denote this collection of differences as *semantic difference*, which is formally defined as

$$\Delta(x, e) = \{o \mid o \in \{x \setminus e\} \cup \{e \setminus x\}\}. \quad (1)$$

The aforementioned set of differences is estimated through a learnable difference detector $D(x, e)$ that, given the original and modified image, predicts a set of object-level differences which serves as an approximation of $\Delta(x, e)$, expressed in terms of RoIs. Notably, this detection process is executed independently of the textual prompt t to ensure that the outcome is not biased by the intended edit.

Coherence Estimation. In the second step, we evaluate each detected difference individually to assess its coherence with the textual prompt. Specifically, a coherence estimator operates on each detected object-level change $o_i \in D(x, e)$, determining whether the visual modifications align with the intended edit \tilde{e} . Formally,

$$C(x, e, t, o_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } o_i \in \tilde{e}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This process enables the differentiation between intended and unintended edits, thereby facilitating a comprehensive and interpretable evaluation of the task.

3.3. Detecting Differences

To build the difference detector and the coherence estimator, we design two novel architectures building upon the

general structure of autoregressive Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs), which offer a sufficiently general framework for encoding images, prompts, and RoIs.

For difference detection, we train an MLLM $D(x, e)$ to predict object-level differences between two images in terms of (i) the type of modification (*i.e.*, addition, removal, edit), (ii) the RoI of the modified region, and (iii) the subjects involved in the modification. Formally, the difference detector operates as:

$$D(x, e) = [(c_i, S_i, b_i)]_{i=1}^k, \quad (3)$$

where c_i denotes a command from $\{\text{ADD}, \text{EDIT}, \text{REMOVE}\}$, S_i describes the modified object in free text, and $b_i \in \mathbb{R}^4$ defines the bounding box coordinates in the format $(x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max})$.

Each tuple (c_i, S_i, b_i) is fully specified in the textual domain, and the model is optimized to output structured text representations of modifications, formatted as: "COMMAND: object, [bb1, bb2, bb3, bb4]". This structured output ensures precise localization and identification of changes.

To estimate the confidence of a predicted RoI, we compute the probability of the predicted command c_i relative to the total probability mass of all possible commands. This confidence measure aligns with conventional object detection confidence estimation techniques [7, 19].

Training Procedure Overview. Our training pipeline consists of two phases: (i) a pre-training stage leveraging real image pairs and (ii) a fine-tuning stage using images modified with inpainting models. Notably, the model is intentionally not trained on instruction-based paired edited images due to two key considerations. First, such training may lead to overfitting to specific editing architectures while underperforming on unseen methods. Second, instruction-edited image pairs would necessitate extensive human annotations for commands and RoIs, introducing significant cost and time constraints.

Stage 1: Learning to Compare Similar Images. In this stage, we instruct the difference detector to identify object-level differences when considering pairs of similar real images. Specifically, the MLLM is trained to predict objects that are not mutually present in both images, leveraging an existing object detection dataset.

In detail, we employ images and object-level annotations from the LVIS dataset [22]. We identify pairs of similar images by computing the cosine similarity in the DINOv2 [38] embedding space, and retaining only those with a cosine similarity greater than 0.6, ensuring high visual similarity. In addition, we make sure that the aforementioned pairs contain at least one common object class and differ by fewer than 15 object classes. This filtering results in a total of 118k image pairs. When encoding image pairs in

this stage, objects present in the first image but absent in the second are labeled as REMOVE, while objects appearing in the second image but not in the first are labeled as ADD. Objects exhibiting an intersection-over-union above a predefined threshold across both images are classified as EDIT. Further details regarding dataset construction are provided in the supplementary material.

Stage 2: Learning to Detect Inpainted Areas. In the second stage, we refine the model by bridging the gap between pre-training on real image pairs and application to edited images. To accomplish this, we select images from the LVIS dataset and sample non-overlapping annotated objects. Starting from LVIS images, we employ inpainting to generate original and edited image pairs. For each object, an operation is randomly selected among {ADD, EDIT, REMOVE}. Inpainting is then performed using LaMa [47]: for the added objects, the corresponding region is inpainted on the original image, while for removed objects, the inpaint is performed on the edited one. For the edit operation, 30% of the edited objects undergo a color change, while the remaining 70% are substituted with a different object. We rely on GPT-4o to generate target objects suitable for substitution by prompting it with a caption of the original image as well as the original object. To perform the edits, the Kandinsky 2.2 inpaint model [42] is employed to inpaint selected regions. This process leads to a training set of 97k elements and a test set of 19k.

3.4. Estimating the Coherence

Given the original and edited image, along with a detected difference, the coherence estimator produces a binary decision (*i.e.*, Yes/No) and a textual rationale indicating whether the modification is coherent with the intended edit. To induce the model to focus on a specific difference, the bounding box of the detected difference is visually depicted on the original and edited image before they are fed to the coherence estimator. Further, we also include the type of modification c_i and its textual description S_i as input to the model.

To train the model, we annotated 116 samples from the EmuEdit [44] test set, with the corresponding edited images generated using InstructDiffusion [18]. For each sample, we manually annotated both the observed differences and a binary coherence indicator. In addition, we employed GPT-4o to generate a rationale for each annotation, which was subsequently refined through human review to eliminate any inaccuracies. While the command c and the subjects S were provided in textual format, the bounding boxes were directly depicted on the images using a color-coded scheme: red for additions, green for edits, and blue for removals. Specifically, additions are superimposed on the edited image, whereas the bounding boxes corresponding to removals and edits are applied solely to the original image.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Implementation and Training Details

In our experiments, we consider three recent MLLMs designed to support multi-image input tasks: Idefics3-8B [30], Qwen2-VL-7B [49], and mPLUG-Owl3-7B [52]. Following the training steps described in Sec. 3.3 and Sec. 3.4, we fine-tune each model using QLoRA [12]. Specifically, the vision encoder and projector of each model remain frozen, while the language model is quantized and augmented with LoRA [24] adapters. LoRA is applied to the self-attention and MLP layers across all 32 Transformer blocks. Further details regarding model configuration and training are provided in the supplementary material.

4.2. Evaluating Detected Differences

To evaluate the performance of our detection and coherence pipeline, we construct a new dataset, termed as DICE-D, specifically designed for the task. This dataset comprises 800 edited images extracted from the I²EBench [35] benchmark. We select images and prompts from a subset of the edit categories that involve object-based modifications, in particular: color alteration, counting (only if involving a single object change), object removal, and object replacement. Each pair of images is manually annotated with detected differences represented as bounding boxes, editing commands (*i.e.*, ADD, REMOVE, EDIT), and textual descriptions. Also, we assign a coherence label for each bounding box to indicate its alignment with the prompt.

Difference Detection Results. We first evaluate the ability of the difference detection model to detect modifications between the original and edited images. Following object detection literature [7, 31], we compute the mean average precision (AP) between predicted and labeled bounding boxes from DICE-D. Specifically, we average results at 10 IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95. Further, we include AP₅₀ (average precision at 50% IoU), AP₇₅ (average precision at 75% IoU), AP_M (for medium-sized objects), and AP_L (for large-sized objects), ensuring a comprehensive evaluation across different object scales and IoU thresholds.

Results are reported in Table 1, where we consider both class-agnostic detection and class-aware detection and compare DICE against other MLLMs and open-vocabulary detectors, OWLv2 [37] and Grounding DINO [33], for which the experimental setup is detailed in the supplementary material. In class-agnostic detection, all predictions are treated as belonging to the same category, to evaluate only the bounding box location. Vice versa, in class-aware detection, both the bounding box location and the editing command are considered, evaluating the accuracy of both the detection and the associated command. As shown, using Idefics as the base model consistently achieves the best performance across all metrics, with an increase of 17.1 and 20.0 in AP

	Confidence	Training		Class-agnostic Detection					Class-aware Detection							
		Stage 1	Stage 2	AP	AP ₅₀	AP ₇₅	AP _M	AP _L	AP	AP ₅₀	AP ₇₅	AP _M	AP _L	AP _{ADD}	AP _{REM}	AP _{EDIT}
<i>Grounding Models</i>																
OWLv2 [37]	✓	-	-	16.4	25.2	17.3	12.4	21.4	9.8	14.0	10.7	9.1	10.6	12.3	7.1	9.8
Grounding DINO [33]	✓	-	-	12.8	17.6	13.4	9.3	15.2	6.8	8.6	7.4	6.1	7.8	4.8	8.6	6.9
<i>Alternative MLLMs</i>																
GlaMM [41]	-	-	-	5.0	8.3	4.8	2.0	6.3	2.7	4.1	2.8	1.1	3.5	3.9	1.3	2.9
GPT-4 [1]	-	-	-	0.5	1.9	0.2	0.0	0.8	0.3	1.1	0.1	0	0.5	1.7	1.9	0.3
Qwen2-VL-7B [49]	-	✓	✓	2.0	5.3	1.3	0.3	3.4	1.6	3.3	1.2	0.1	2.4	0.1	0.1	3.2
Qwen2-VL-7B [49]	✓	✓	✓	2.3	5.6	1.8	0.1	3.5	1.6	4.1	1.1	0	1.6	0.1	0.1	3.2
mPLUG-Owl3-7B [52]	-	✓	✓	3.8	10.3	2.4	0.5	5.1	2.5	6.7	1.7	0.3	3.3	1.1	1.5	5.1
mPLUG-Owl3-7B [52]	✓	✓	✓	5.2	13.7	3.2	0.5	7.3	4.4	10.6	3.1	0.3	5.5	0.1	7.3	4.8
<i>Ablation Studies</i>																
Idefics3-8B [30]	-	-	✓	15.1	30.1	13.4	8.5	18.6	9.4	18.1	9.3	5.5	11.0	7.3	7.5	13.4
Idefics3-8B [30]	-	✓	✓	16.7	30.7	16.0	10.4	20.3	10.6	17.9	10.9	6.6	12.5	7.4	7.7	16.5
Idefics3-8B [30]	✓ _{rand}	✓	✓	16.8	31.2	16.2	10.3	20.5	9.7	16.5	10.0	6.7	11.2	7.0	7.9	14.2
Idefics3-8B [30]	✓	✓	-	2.9	5.1	2.8	1.9	4.2	1.4	2.2	1.4	0.9	1.8	2.0	0.4	1.8
Idefics3-8B [30]	✓	-	✓	18.2	36.8	16.0	9.8	22.7	12.2	22.2	12.1	7.3	15.3	7.2	13.4	15.8
DICE (Ours)																
Idefics3-8B [30]	✓	✓	✓	22.3	40.1	21.9	13.5	36.8	15.5	24.8	16.5	11.4	15.4	19.6	14.8	16.4

Table 1. Performance comparison of various MLLMs in the difference detection stage of our pipeline, evaluated under both class-agnostic and class-aware settings. Results are presented in terms of AP metrics across various training configurations.

	Confidence	Coherence over		Coherence over		
		GT Areas	Detected Areas	AP	AP ₅₀	AP ₇₅
		Accuracy	AP	AP ₅₀	AP ₇₅	
<i>Alternative MLLMs</i>						
Qwen2-VL-7B [49]	-	76.6	1.4	3.8	0.6	
Qwen2-VL-7B [49]	✓	76.6	1.8	4.9	0.9	
mPLUG-Owl3-7B [52]	-	85.9	3.8	10.0	2.4	
mPLUG-Owl3-7B [52]	✓	85.9	4.5	11.3	2.9	
DICE (Ours)						
Idefics3-8B [30]	-	85.4	12.0	20.3	12.0	
Idefics3-8B [30]	✓	85.4	15.5	26.0	16.1	

Table 2. Performance comparison of various MLLMs in the coherence estimation stage of our pipeline. Coherence accuracy is measured using ground-truth differences, while coherence over detected areas employs the output of the first stage of our pipeline and is evaluated using AP metrics.

in a class-agnostic setting compared to Qwen and mPLUG. Similarly, when considering the command labels, Idefics outperforms Qwen and mPLUG by 11.8 and 13.9. This superior performance may be attributed to the distinctive image encoding pipeline employed by Idefics, in which each image is resized to a larger dimension and segmented into a grid of crops, each encoded independently. Although this approach increases the amount of visual information processed, the grid-based encoding simultaneously introduces a localization factor to the captured visual details that can be leveraged in a task of detection. Further, the inferior performance of OWLv2 [37] and Grounding DINO [33] underscores that difference detection is fundamentally distinct from standard object detection.

When validating the contribution of the key components of our pipeline, it is worth noting that the initial pre-

training stage significantly contributes to the final performance. Specifically, training Idefics in both stages results in improvements of 1.6 and 1.2 in class-agnostic and class-aware AP, respectively, compared to training solely on the second stage dataset. Notably, even training exclusively on the first stage enhances class-agnostic detection compared to Qwen (*i.e.*, +0.4 AP). This observation implies that predicting missing objects in pairs of similar real images not only facilitates the learning of prediction syntax but also enables the transfer of relevant knowledge to the difference detection task in edited images.

Moreover, incorporating the extracted confidence score enhances difference localization results, with improvements of 5.5 and 3.1 AP observed for Idefics-based models trained on both stages and solely on the second stage respectively, compared to using a fixed confidence value of 1. Additionally, using random confidence values results in worse performance, further indicating that the uncertainty in the command correlates with the actual prediction confidence.

Coherence Estimation Results. The coherence estimation model assesses whether each detected difference is correctly aligned with the prompt using a binary prediction (*i.e.*, Yes/No). Moreover, the coherence step incorporates explicit model reasoning [51], improving the interpretability of the results. Under this setting, models are evaluated on DICE-D, in terms of coherence over ground-truth areas and coherence over detected areas. To measure the coherence accuracy, ground-truth differences are fed into the coherence estimator, and results are evaluated against the manually annotated coherence. Instead, for the coherence over detected areas, the performance of DICE is measured through AP, considering the coherence label of the differ-

Editing Models	Correct Edits		Unwanted Edits		No Visual Change	
	DICE (%) \uparrow	Humans (1-5) \uparrow	DICE (%) \downarrow	Humans (1-5) \uparrow	DICE (%) \downarrow	Humans (%) \downarrow
HIVE [55]	11.0	2.0	40.5	3.1	54.5	40.5
InstructPix2Pix [4]	15.5	2.3	32.1	3.3	44.0	22.0
MGIE [16]	23.0	2.7	21.6	3.8	11.5	10.0
MagicBrush [54]	24.5	2.9	23.1	3.9	8.5	5.5
InstructDiffusion [18]	30.0	3.0	19.1	4.0	13.5	10.5

Table 3. Benchmark comparison of model rankings generated by DICE and those derived from the user study. The first two columns contrast average human ratings with scores obtained using DICE. The final column compares the percentage of unchanged images in the user study – cases with maximal background preservation and minimal prompt adherence – to the corresponding one identified by DICE.

ence as the ground-truth category of the bounding box. This is done by extracting differences with the detector and subsequently predicting the coherence of each difference.

Results are summarized in Table 2, evaluating various MLLMs as coherence estimators. Idefics consistently achieves the highest overall performance on AP, surpassing mPLUG and Qwen by 11.0 and 12.7 points, respectively, while maintaining comparable coherence accuracy. Additionally, incorporating confidence from the difference detection stage into the AP computation leads to performance improvements across all evaluated MLLMs. This highlights the importance of confidence extraction in the difference detection phase and motivates further research on aligning token probability with confidence estimation in object detection. Based on these results, Idefics3-8B is selected as the base MLLM for DICE in all subsequent experiments.

4.3. Evaluation of Image Editing Models

User Study Details. We conduct a user study to evaluate our proposed framework within the context of instruction-based image editing. In detail, we collect 200 prompts along with their corresponding original images, 50% from MagicBrush [54] and 50% from I²EBench [35]. For MagicBrush, we use GPT-4o to filter out prompts that do not involve object modification. Differently, for the I²EBench subset, we employ the same selection criteria as in the construction of DICE-D (cf. Sec. 4.2). We select five state-of-the-art generators and generate 200 edited images per generator. Specifically, our model selection includes HIVE [55], InstructPix2Pix [4], MGIE [16], MagicBrush [54], and InstructDiffusion [18]. To assess the quality of the generated edits, we asked 10 human annotators to evaluate each sample on two dimensions: *prompt adherence* and *background preservation*. Prompt adherence measures how well the modifications in the edited image align with the instructions given in the prompt. Differently, background preservation assesses how well the elements that were not intended to be modified remained unchanged. Ratings for each dimension were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale. We refer the user to the supplementary materials for more detailed information about the user study.

Editing Model Ranking. To evaluate the performance of

editing models, we establish three axes to rank the considered generators using DICE. *Correct edits* measure the percentage of images in which at least one detected difference is classified as coherent. Conversely, *unwanted edits* quantify the percentage of the total image area containing differences marked as non-coherent. Lastly, *no visual change* represents the percentage of images where DICE does not detect any visual alteration, potentially due to insufficient prompt clarity, lack of understanding, or inability of the model to execute the requested modification. Notably, *correct* and *unwanted edits* can be measured with the average prompt adherence and background preservation ratings from the user study. Similarly, from the user study, *no visual change* is assessed by identifying images rated 5 in background preservation and 1 in prompt following.

In Table 3, we compare the rankings generated by our evaluation with those obtained from the user study. As it can be seen, model rankings from DICE align with human evaluations. In particular, InstructDiffusion and MagicBrush emerge as the top-performing models both according to DICE and human ratings, excelling in performing correct modifications while effectively preserving the background. Likewise, the ranking order for *no visual change* remains consistent across DICE and the user study, further validating the reliability of our approach.

To qualitatively validate the predictions of DICE, Fig. 3 presents editing samples showcasing difference detection and coherence predictions across various prompts and models. Notably, DICE effectively identifies image differences and evaluates their coherence with the editing prompt.

Correlation with Human Judgment. To further validate the alignment between the detected differences and human judgment, we integrate DICE predictions within CLIP-based evaluation metrics measuring image similarity (CLIP-I) for background preservation and image-text similarity (CLIP-T) for prompt adherence [23]. In particular, CLIP-I measures the similarity between the original and the edited image. To compute CLIP-T, instead, we caption the original image using an MLLM (*i.e.*, Idefics3-8B in our experiments) and feed the extracted caption along with the editing prompt to GPT-4o to produce a caption of the ideal edited image (*i.e.*, target caption). Through CLIP-T we then

Figure 3. Qualitative samples of DICE applied on images edited by MGIE [16] and InstructDiffusion [18] models.

	ρ	ρ_s	τ
<i>Background Preservation</i>			
CLIP-I	51.1	42.9	33.3
w/ patch on random areas	34.2	25.6	19.4
w/ patch on all detected differences	32.7	15.6	11.6
w/ DICE (patch on coherent differences)	54.5	45.4	35.1
<i>Prompt Adherence</i>			
CLIP-T	21.5	23.1	17.1
w/ patch on random areas	17.8	19.5	14.3
w/ patch on all detected differences	13.3	14.6	10.7
w/ DICE (patch on non-coherent differences)	24.6	26.6	19.6

Table 4. Correlation analysis showing improved alignment with human judgment when integrating DICE in CLIP-I and CLIP-T.

measure the CLIP similarity between the target caption and the actual edited image. To integrate DICE in CLIP-I and CLIP-T, we modify both the original and edited images by selectively masking specific regions, taking into account DICE predictions. Specifically, for background preservation, we mask coherent differences, whereas, for prompt adherence assessment, non-coherent differences are patched.

For this experiment, we compare the correlation scores of standard CLIP-I and CLIP-T metrics with those obtained by masking original and edited images using DICE. Results are shown in Table 4, where we measure Spearman’s ρ , Pearson’s ρ_s , and Kendall’s τ correlation coefficients between automated evaluation scores and human judgment. We also compare when randomly masking areas from the differences detected by DICE, or when masking all detected differences, including both coherent and non-coherent changes. As it can be seen, DICE effectively enhances the correlation of both CLIP-I and CLIP-T metrics with human ratings. Specifically, for background preservation, CLIP-I exhibits the strongest correlation with hu-

man judgments when masking only coherent differences, achieving a Pearson’s score of 54.5. This is a significant improvement over the baseline score of 51.1 (no masking), and substantially higher than the scores obtained with random masking or masking all detected differences. This result suggests that excluding correctly modified regions allows CLIP-I to better focus on the actual background, producing a metric that more accurately aligns with human perception.

For prompt adherence, CLIP-T shows better correlation when we patch non-coherent differences, achieving a Pearson’s score of 24.6, compared to 21.5 without masking. Instead, masking all differences leads to a drop to 13.3, likely due to indiscriminate removal of both erroneous and correct edits. This outlines that selectively removing only incorrect modifications helps CLIP-T focus on prompt-relevant changes, thus improving alignment with human evaluations.

Overall, these results demonstrate that DICE enhances the reliability of CLIP-based metrics, making them more aligned with human perception of editing quality. In particular, distinguishing between coherent and non-coherent changes is crucial for obtaining meaningful evaluations.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we introduced DICE: a novel approach to evaluate instruction-guided image editing by detecting and assessing object-level differences between original and edited images. Our method leverages MLLMs to detect semantic differences between images and determine their coherence with the given editing instructions. This dual-step process allows for a structured and interpretable evaluation, addressing both the accuracy of the detected modifications and their semantic alignment with user intent.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high-performance computing resources. This work has been supported by the EU Horizon projects “ELSA - European Lighthouse on Safe and Secure AI” (No. 101070617), “ELIAS - European Lighthouse of AI for Sustainability” (No. 101120237) and “ELLIOT - European Large Open Multi-Modal Foundation Models For Robust Generalization On Arbitrary Data Streams” (No. 101214398), and by the PNRRM4C2 project “FAIR - Future Artificial Intelligence Research” funded by the EU - NextGenerationEU.

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